

Globalization and Public Policy Analysis: A Case Study of Foreign Policy of ASEAN Member States

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Abstract—This study has an objective to analyze foreign policy of member states in globalization current, aiming to answer that the foreign policy of member states have been changed or remained the same and there are any factors affecting changing of foreign policy of the member states.

From the study results, it is found that the foreign policy of Thailand is a friendly foreign policy with all states. The policy of Indonesia is more opened because of a change in leader, allowing more democratic development in the country; the government has proceeded with friendly foreign policy with the states in order to bring funds into the state. The foreign policy of Malaysia is not much changed as there is no changing in the leader; the policy of Malaysia has reconciled relations with main city of Indian and Chinese residing in the country in order to bring investments into the country and to relieve tensions in the country. The foreign policy of the Philippines has proceeded with policy under the ASEAN framework and emphasized on international Islam communities. The foreign policy of Singapore has the least changed as the Singapore's policy focuses on internal trade since the state was found. As for the foreign policy of Brunei Darussalam, Brunei has a little role in the international stage; the state having closest relationship as from the view of history is Singapore as the Singaporean has invested in retailing business in Brunei. The foreign policy of Vietnam has emphasized on an omnidirectional foreign policy in order to compete with several states in global stage. The foreign policy of Myanmar has proceeded with a friendly foreign policy with all ASEAN member states, the East-west Corridor transportation line from Myanmar through Thailand and Lao to Vietnam has been developed. As for the foreign policy of Lao, In 2001, the Thai government and Lao government held a discussion which Thailand reaffirmed the position not to support the anti-Lao group. The foreign policy of Cambodia has proceeded with more openness, having good relation with China, Russia and USA as these states has invested in the state, especially the US company.

Keywords—Globalization, Public Policy Analysis, Foreign Policy, ASEAN Member States.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE world in the age of globalization is the expansion of investment in all regions of the world, motivated by the development of information technology (IT) connecting the whole world. Information technology and globalization creates the borderless world as the result from connection with all parts of the world together by information technology system. Such trading, investment and expansion affect the structure of nation-states in many parts of the current which cannot defend themselves in economics and politics when comparing with the nation-states in Superpower level, namely the United States of America or European Union, causing the collective

nation-states to be created integration for economics in FTA framework or common market meaning the mechanism of sovereignty reduction or “Regional State”.

In the year of 1967, a stimulation for integration happened in the Southeast Asia region. The leaders in that time were Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines and Singapore. The establishment of ASEAN rendered several states to be united for defending an intervention from Superpowers and to cooperate in economic and society development of the region. On August 8, 1967, the declaration of oath of ASEAN was happened in order to accelerate the developments of economics, society, culture of the region, as well as, promote peace and mutual cooperation in transportation, education; moreover, ASEAN was declared as peaceful, liberal, neutral zone in Malaysia on November 27, 1971 to guarantee that there will be no intervention of Superpower [1].

ASEAN developed the FTA (Free Trade Area) in November, 2000; They affirmed to determine FTA and investment to be successful, having a mutual taxation agreement, standard and quality of communication equipment, cosmetics and privilege according to agreement [2]; the first 6 states started in 2003 and completed in 2005, the new members in Indochina and Myanmar had to start in 2008 and had to complete in 2010; however, the establishment of FTA was still not completed as expected due to differences in several basis in each countries in the region, such as trading, investment, infrastructure and identical products. In addition from internal trading, there were a cooperation with East Asia, namely ASEAN+3 (ASEAN+ China, Japan and Korea) on June 24, 2001 in order to cooperate in investment with each other; therefore, these 3 are were the Superpowers in ASEAN as if they are capitalists coming to seize interests from ASEAN. If ASEAN could not strengthen the group, especially the China coming into every corner of Asia, Europe and America, ASEAN should have their own strategy to solve problems in the future.

On September 11, 2001, the agreement in ministerial level regarding international terrorism at Hanoi was made and member states agreed to form a mutual terrorism defense in 7th summit at Brunei, so-called 2000 ASEAN Declaration; each state shall form a mutual defense in terrorism; however, which states would receive a military force to support in military exercise, it will depend on an agreement in such state [3].

Cooperation of ASEAN has more diversity in this globalized world, which can be noticed from international communication cooperation in order to cooperate and mutually create international news in order to reduce expenses and to allow government sector and private sector to aware the

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importance of e-ASEAN, which would benefit to trading and investment [4].

Cooperation in Southeast Asia from cold-war era to globalization era is changed very much from the cooperation of political security and mono-function to be the integration in the region without the intervention of Superpower, such as ASEAN. This ASEAN creates “sub-regional” of cities of states having close history and culture and trading for a long time; moreover, there is cooperation with nations outside of the group, namely Europe, Japan and China. All of these aim to be cooperation in APEC and to WTO, which is supranational and bring the new regionalism.

However, although having cooperation in the regions, the world economics should not overlook the gradually increasing role of multi-national corporation from government as a center. Globalization is the reason causing the region, politics to be gradually intervened or undermined by multi-national corporation, the global market will be beyond borderland. Regionalism should not discriminate between trading in the regions and outside of the regions; economist tends to see them as regional trading bloc and think that the best cooperation is multilateral trade liberalization while the other group of academician overlooks a political reason but thinks that the economic integration of states is an economic interest according to the principle of economics, thinking that the economic integration rendering better efficiency and offshoring from inside of nations to trading nation having better efficiency [5].

The policy purpose, control of term regarding the highest benefit matter would be determined by competent authority bringing history, economics, politics and psychology to be regulations; surely, the competent authority may make the policy to be benefited in the term of state, behavior of the states in Southeast Asia; therefore, it is necessary to determine a significant indicator in state towards international behavior of state.

Outcome results from the determination of policy will depend on a capability of each state having influence over decision making and operations by other states. The tools in the determination of foreign policy applied in Southeast Asia are an old state determination, namely a diplomacy procedure into persuasion for integration creating strength. These tools are applied in unilateral country, bilateral countries and multilateral states throughout ASEAN. All of these indicate that the procedure in relationships between states in Southeast Asia is not united harmoniously in this region.

Southeast Asia does not have the power over core nation-states in capability creation in determination and applicable power over national system but the nation-states themselves that can select the tools of policy which is important to the most benefit of nation as it will determine a level of conflict, competition and cooperation in relationships with other states [6].

As aforementioned problems and importance, the researcher, therefore, has the interest to analyzing the foreign policy of ASEAN member states in globalization current in order to answer that the foreign policy is changed or still

preserved a former policy and find the factors affecting the change of the foreign policy of ASEAN member states.

II. OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to analyze the foreign policy of ASEAN member states in the current globalization.

III. DELIMITATION OF RESEARCH

The research of globalization and public policy analysis: a case study of foreign policy of Thailand has a unit in research analysis, namely foreign policy of ASEAN member states; the scope of time in the study is A.D. 2000-2014. However, this research has a limitation in the aspects of time and resource; thus, the researcher is unable to study the foreign policy of ASEAN member states completely and is able to, only, present the material and corresponding issue with education matter.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Adaption of ASEAN Concept:** The adaption of ASEAN is the concept that ASEAN member states must proceed with international economic policy in trading and finance mutually to increase the power in negotiation in economics and politics; the trading policy must expand the cooperation in 2 levels: first, the expansion of FTA must be done in order to expand the trading in the member states and to reduce a reliance on USA and EU market, second, the development to the form of common market; as for the financial policy, Asian Monetary Fund must be established hastily in order to be a financial organization in Asia member states having the role as IMF. In long term, ASEAN should develop mutual economics in the form of Asian Economic Union as the Asian Economic Union would lead to a mutual economic policy, financial policy and treasury policy and common currency [7].
2. **Sub-regional Concept:** Joseph Nye said that the regional relation was an interaction between certain number of states having geographical relation and dependency level from each other; moreover, George Liska also said that regarding integration, the similarity of factors of social characteristics, popularity, belief and social structure had to be in relation for a long time, such as sub-regional groups in ASEAN which are situated closely; having history, customs, culture and trading for a long time, it should create a better understanding than in large group, for example BIMP-EAGA (Brunei Darussalam-Indonesia-Malaysia-Philippines-East ASEAN Growth Area), IMS-GT Triangle, IMT-GT (Indonesia-Malaysia-Thailand Growth Triangle), WEC (West-East Corridor), Mekong Basin in Vietnam, Lao, Cambodia, Thai under the development plan of ASEAN Mekong Basin Development Cooperation Scheme, which includes China [8].
3. **Game Theory:** This theory is a guideline to describe the decision making behavior in procedure of public policy,

which covers in foreign policy procedure. Game Theory utilized in the analysis in this article is “Zero Sum Game” and “Non-zero Sum Game” divided into “Positive Sum Game” and “Negative Sum Game”; Zero Sum Game means a guideline in decision making based on winner and loser; Negative Sum Game which is in the part of Non-zero Sum Game means a theory framework of decision making based on the event when the results of the decision making every party to be a loser which those decision makers attempt to avoid such decision making; Positive Sum Game is a guideline of Non-zero Sum Game having important principle which describes the decision based on the reason and results that the decision maker has to attempt to find the guideline giving Win-win results in decision making of all parties, namely situation assessment of themselves and other party or several parties and find the way of point of confluence in benefits in every party, which we call “Positive Sum Game”

4. **Decision Making Theory:** This theory applied in foreign policy procedure could be divided into a decision making theory based on Legal Approach, describing that the consideration of decision making is in accordance with the legislation defined by law and based on “Behavioral Approach”, describing that although foreign policy procedure is stipulated in laws, in the practical way of decision making may be in accordance with the stipulated laws. Moreover, the decision making theory also emphasizes on psychology, that is to say, it is a psychological study and attitude of decision maker. In such framework, it is described that foreign policy will be created from characteristics of thought or idea of leader and considered as “Input” in certain level even not 100%.
5. **System Approach Theory:** the concept in system approach theory for describing behavior of foreign policy procedure is a Balance of Power of Superpowers, which is the behavior described as in framework in last decade so-called “Balancing Power System”, that is to say, systematic theorist make a hypothesis that in each system, the Superpowers would have the framework in foreign policy procedure and when such framework is changed, the behavior in foreign policy procedure might be changed [9].

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. This research is an exploratory research as ex post facto research and utilizes qualitative research by documentary research studying and research academic document in both Thai and foreign documents.
2. Data collection from the documentary research was collected from the study and research of Thai and foreign academic document in electronic form and non-electronic form, which has been printed or published to public, namely seminar documents, thesis, research results in academic journal in Public Administration field in Thai and foreign languages.
3. Inspection and data analysis: the inspection is to prove a reliability whether the obtained results is corrected or not

by utilizing data triangulation to prove whether the obtained data is correct or not. The methods are to inspect data source from personal source, time source and place source in order to inspect whether the obtained data are identical and reliable or not [10]. As for the data analysis, the researcher utilized content analysis in data analysis by utilizing ideal framework considered from the review of literature to be a guideline in data analysis.

VI. RESULTS

The research results of foreign policy of ASEAN member states in globalization, it is found that:

Thai foreign policy is to be friendly with all states; in the Thaksin government era, the policy is to proceed in good relation with ASEAN group and China and use a Forward Engagement Policy with Asia states by promoting mutual projects or Asia Cooperation Dialogue (ACD) with ASEAN states, South Asia, East Asia in order to drive a dialogue in the issue related to economics connection and also to support Tri partie Cooperation.

In the era of Aphisit government, The Ministry of Vejajjiva Foreign Affairs under the lead of Mr. Kasit Piromya pushed a policy of relation creation in ASEAN which becomes the important policy of integration of ASEAN community today. A conflict with Cambodia in the matter of Temple of Pra Vihear and the commotion in Thailand in that time reduced an image and reliability of Thailand in international stage.

In the era of Yingluck one of Shinawatra government, the main foreign policy was a restoration of confidence and image of Thailand to be returned in to positive way in the eyes of international community. There were a visit of Thai Prime Minister in foreign countries for responding to the visit in bilateral countries and traveling to participate in 26 meetings in the past year, demonstrating that the foreign countries see the importance of Thailand.

Mr. Barack Obama, the President of United States of America chose to visit Thailand first after he inaugurated the office as the President for the second time even if this happened in the year-end of 2555, Mr. Shizo Abe, the President of Japan chose to visit Thailand first after he inaugurated the office as the president for the second time at the beginning of 2013, and, even, Mr. Wang Yi, the Minister of Department of Foreign Affairs chose to visit Thailand first after he inaugurated the office; moreover, he visited Thailand several opportunities in the same year. These events indicate whether the Superpowers return to value Thailand again or not [11].

Kajit Jittasevi said that The policy and international relation of Thailand at the present time were “a caution that Thailand is an opened state that takes transnational currents; therefore, unwanted local problems to be an internal problems or regarding as “internal affairs” to be limited for not allowing “external states” to intervene are not possible anymore as in the connected world in the transnational relation currents, events that happened in local level can turn to be a “Global Issues” and Thai state has to adjust with a connection of local to global which is the one of relation model today” [12].

The foreign policy of Indonesia is more opened because of change in leader rendering the state to develop into democracy. The government proceeds with friendly policy with several states in order to bring funds into the state. The relation with ASEAN is still in the ASEAN framework, and in the visit of ASEAN group, the leader tried to mention a mutual terrorism defense in this region. A state having the closest relation with Indonesia is Singapore because of the investment that Singapore bring into the country. Singapore often helps Indonesia in finance and item to protect its benefits and help neighboring states of ASEAN. The policy of Indonesia focuses on economic development and democracy in the state for creating internal stability and attracting the investment into the state from Asia, Europe and USA. Moreover, Indonesia have reached the agreement of maritime demarcation overlapping in Midanao Sea and Celebes Sea successfully after negotiating for 20 years, creating a great model of territorial disputes that be able to settle with negotiation that is not needed to use military force [13].

Indonesia has the developmental plan or MP3EI by current president: Mr.Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono. Indonesia will country in 2028 and are developin-reach a developedg to such point. Such model plan stipulates 3 main targets: 1. increasing of production of VAT goods and standard for production process of industrial products, as well as, increasing of utility access and human resource for industry sector 2. Stimulating to create efficient production and developing market to integrate domestic market for national competition 3.Supporting strength for innovation research in production process and market targeting for global competition sustainably. Indonesia aims for rather large target and experiences with many obstacles due to geographical conditions of insel, slow bureaucracy, corruption and high population in the top level of the world; however, the one of policy indicates that Indonesia starts proceeding with such model plan, namely curfew of raw ore but being able to export if such ore is processed to increase value for the products. Attractively, the election for new president would continue the plan whether being tangible or not. The one of two important candidates have declared clearly that they are going to continue this model plan surely, but, believably, anyone who come to hold the office, is going to continue such plan because not only being beneficial to the national economic, the new president would gain more votes and popularity [14].

The foreign policy of Malaysia is not change considerably because there is no change in leader. The policy of Malaysia has adjusted the relation with main land of Indian and Chinese in the state in order to bring investment into the state and to relieve domestic tension. The relation with ASEAN member states is under 2 sub-regional group, namely SIJORI (Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia) and EAGA BIMP (Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines); all 4 nations are mutually look for terrorism for each other. Regarding the relation with USA, after September 11, 2001, Malaysia sympathizes with USA as the victim; both states have investments with each other. Malaysia has declared the vision of 2020 by Former Prime Minister Mahathir bin Mohamadsince 1991; the

Former Prime Minster is regarded as broad-viewed vision leader setting aims for Malaysia to be a developed-country in 2020 as the citizen must have an income for 15,000 Dollar per year which the data from World Bank of 2010 shows that the income was 10,432 Dollar and tended to increase. Malaysia is the state having high efficient economics, systematic development not only economics but human resource development and other [15].

The leader of USA came to visit Kuala Lumpur of Malaysia for the first time in 48 years for holding discussion regarding negotiation of Pacific Strategic Economic Partnership -Trans Agreement: TPP; Mr.Obama and the Prime Minister, Najib

Abdul Razakhad the same opinion in respect to maritime dispute settlement by enforcing international maritime laws together with stating that ASEAN members and China must cooperate to build a practical guideline regarding South China Sea. However, Malaysia could not support USA at its full power as the problematic events with China have recently occurred: Malaysia Airline, Flight: HM 370 being disappeared; originally, the economic relation with China was firm and tight, it is clouded by this event [16].

The foreign policy of Philippines is changed for the original one instead of conservative policy emphasizing on internal factors. Arroyo-Gloria Macapagalephasizes on making friendly relation with several states and mainly inherits the policy of the former president, Ramos, that is to say, diplomatic negotiation in order to draw development into the state. The policy is proceeded under the ASEAN framework and emphasizes on international Islam community by making the relation with OIC in order to allow such organization to help in reconciliation with secessionist group in the South territory or MILF. Regarding the relation in the ASEAN group, Arroyo recovered trading and investment in economic triangle EAGA. For the relation with USA after terrorist attack in September 11, the foreign policy of Philippines towards USA gained closer relation than any other states in the region as Philippines sympathized with USA and cooperated and looked for terrorism. USA provided supports for Philippines in funds for developing south region and sent military force to have exercises with Philippines' military force.

In March 2014, the President, Benigno Simeon Cojuangco Aquino(the leader of Philippines) and Mr.Murak Ibrahim, the leader of MIFL Secessionist jointly signed a peace agreement of MILF after negotiating for 17 years at the President House in Manila City, having the Prime Minister, ajib Abdul RazakN (the leader of Malaysia) as a witness on behalf of the state providing coordination between 2 parties to reach an agreement successfully [17].

The President, Benigno Simeon Cojuangco Aquino(the leader of Philippines) prepares to meet Shinzo Abe, the Prime Minister of Japan on June 24, 2014. The two states would emphasize on a regional cooperation development for each other. Regarding strategic cooperation, After Manila City visit of Mr.Abe which Japan provided supports in Philippines' naval officer; the event corresponded to the tension between Japan and China regarding maritime dispute as well. For the

last week, Japan summoned Chinese ambassador after an encounter of jet-fighter between 2 states near disputed areas, the archipelagocalled “Senkaku” by Japan or “Diaoyudao” by China [18].

Mr.Obama stayed in Philippines for 2 days (April 28-29) in order to discuss with Benigno Simeon Cojuangco Aquino III (The President) and met with USA soldier deployed at Philippines. As Mr.Obama arrived at Philippines, Mr.Voltaire Gazmin, the Minister of Defense, and USA ambassador at Philippines, Mr.Philp Goldberg jointly signed Enhanced (Defense Cooperation Agreement (EDCA)having periodfor years, which increases the military role of USA 10military in Philippines, including accessing to base, harbor and airport. Other than the joint exercises, previously there were Filipino group demonstrate against Mr.Obama and disagreed with such agreement as they saw it as moving backward in democracy developed in good way after closing main base of USA in Philippines at the beginning of decade of 1990 [19].

The President, Benigno Simeon Cojuangco Aquino(the leader of Philippines), said before he left to participate in ASEAN 24th summit at Naypyidaw, Myanmar that he uested the leaders of ASEANreqmmember states to face and fight with China who has claimed the ownership over territory in South China Sea, the area which ignited quarrelsome relation between China and Philippines, Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Vietnam and Brunei for 10 years. Moreover, it is getting worse after the Philippines' police apprehend China fishing boat in May 2014 [20].

At the same time, the tension situation between China and Philippines stalemated at South China Sea territorial waters or near Johnson Coral Reefs which was risky for encounter as well after Philippines' court indicted crews of the Chinese fishing boat, who was apprehended by Philippines' authority as for the intrusion in such territorial waters. Moreover, recently, “the President, BenignoSimeon Cojuangco Aquino ”, the leader of Philippines declared that the problems of ASEAN region could not be solved in bilateral framework, but they had to depend on international arbitration judgment instead [21].

The foreign policy of Singapore, Singapore has the least change of foreign policy because the policy of Singapore aims at trading and investment in the state since established. States had the closest relation with Singapore: Malaysia and Indonesia under the sub-regional SIJORI; moreover, Singapore had to depend on oil purchase from Malaysia and Malaysia depended on investment of Singapore. From the meeting between Lee Kuan Yew and Mahathir Mohamad in September 2001, Malaysia agreed to allow Singapore a and Singapore purchasing oild to 2061. As for Indonesi reached an agreementbetween e acho theras Indonesia allowingSingapore to buy natural gas for next 20 years. As for the East Asia, Singapore established Free Trade with Japan, helping Singapore to gain benefits in investment and export of electornic goods and chemical petroleum and e rights equal to Japanese Singaporean company would have th company in all respect. Singapore has promotion policy in .trading and investment with Iraq recentlyThe reason why

Singapore supported USA was in order to gain security benefits and trading and investment that would gain from .AUS

Hsien Loong of Singapore and eeL ,The Prime Minister Najib Abdul Razak, leader of Malaysia hold a.Mrtwodays meeting, they could reach an agreement regardinghigh speed train connected with Kuala Lumpur City in Malaysia. The meeting focused on connection of transportation route and development of Iskandar area in Malaysia and mentioned the establishment of 1 joint checkpoint. The surveys of possibility of new initiative idea are now in progress; customs office, immigration office or CIQ of Singapore and Malaysia situated at the same area. The leaders stimulated to perceive necessity in cooperation in order to develop the Iskandar Project in Malaysia, which generates the benefits for both states. Mr. Lee said that the construction of factory here could help in more employment creation [22].

Reform of trading system by rule of law of Singapore demonstrated clearly and tangibly in trading facilitation. Singapore had the laws stipulated steps in import and export clearly not depending on the discretion of customs authority; moreover, documentation and period of review of export and import documentation had less time. In addition, whenever the government wishes to make an amendment in laws, a declaration will be conduct to inform the private sector in advance; therefore, they can plan and adjust operation strategy to be in conformity with the changed laws affecting Singapore to be ranked by World Bank having attractive factors of investment at first rank of the world in 2013.

Singapore was recognized as low corruption rate state; the study results of the connection of corruption and capability of transportation of Transparency International, it is found that low rate corruption states have the high capability in development of transportation business while high rate corruption states would experience problems in business operation of transportation [23].

The foreign policy of Brunei Darussalam, Brunei is the country having a little role in international stage. Brunei was the host of regional meeting for two times. Brunei has the policy of joint venture with Malaysia, Indonesia and Philippines in economic triangle area of EAGA (East ASEAN Growth Area). Both Mrs. Megawati and Arroyohave visited Brunei in order to negotiate cooperation between each other. The state having closest relationship from the history is Singapore as the Singaporean has invested in retailing business in Brunei.

Brunei has its own economic vision as His Majesty Sultan Haji Hassanal Bolkihahdeclared the vision in 2008, having its official name as “Wawasan Brunei 2035” by the year of 2035, Brunei aims to be the successful state in education and citizen having high skill level, then life quality and dynamic and sustainable economics. Certainly, Brunei issued a strategic plan to reach such goal as follows: 1.education strategy 2.economic strategy 3.security strategy 4.development of private and official institute strategy 5.local development strategy 6.infrastructure development strategy 7.social security strategy and 8. Environmental strategy [24].

The foreign policy of Vietnam is to develop both Lao and Cambodia in order to keep China out, and it is possible that Vietnam has the policy to recreate Indochina group as in the past; however, this creation of group is possible to be an economic energy group to negotiate with original ASEAN group than political power in Cold War era. Vietnam emphasizes on omnidirectional foreign policy to compete with states in international stage.

After Vietnam became ASEAN's member in 1995, an adjustment for modernizing policy and diplomacy in order to gain national benefits by utilizing ASEAN as the base to create network and expand relation with states for increasing recognition in international politics, attracting investment funds from all around the world. Before the abrupt reform occurred in Myanmar two years ago, Vietnam was the "Darling" of international stage.

At the present time, Vietnam wants to be a leader of ASEAN; Vietnam knows very well that ASEAN could help in supporting diplomatic power; moreover, Vietnam attempts to recover relation with the old friend or Russia after disappearing from each other for a long time. The President, Vladimir Putin has a plan to visit Vietnam in this week, which stirs up in diplomacy sector in ASEAN because he refused to participate in East Asia summit at Brunei in last October.

The leader of Vietnam believes that the state has the power and diplomatic influence enough to draw Lao, Cambodia and Myanmar not to be under the power of Superpowers coming in to Southeast Asia, especially China. Deeply, Vietnam scares that ASEAN would lack unity, not solidarity and disunity [25].

Currently, Vietnam are in documentary preparation procedure to file a lawsuit to International Court of Justice in the case of China claims over South China Sea and waits for suitable time for instituting a case. Nevertheless, the stance of the leader declaring to fight with China in court instance occurred from pressure of people who wish to strike back China strongly as Chinese boats circled and collide with Vietnam cargo ship in May 2014 near Paracel Islands far from Chinese oil platform only 12 miles; however, such activity ignites worrisome wave that these would not only affect the relation between both states but would affect economics of Vietnam as China is the biggest trading partner of Vietnam [26].

The foreign policy of Myanmar proceeds with friendly policy with all states in ASEAN; Myanmar are developing East-West Corridor from Myanmar through Thailand and Lao to Vietnam, making all 4 states having close relation that would be beneficial to sub-regional trading and investment in the future. Current problems of Myanmar are the human right issues.

After becoming the opened state and, even, releasing political prisoner and the leader of government resistance, Aung San Suu Kyi shook hand as symbolism with the President, As Aung San Suu Kyi went to have a .Thein Sein speech in parliament, university's meeting hall, Burmese community in foreign states all around the world. The results have been shown off in several years in Myanmar, namely in 2011, there was a suspension of project of power-generated

dam construction, Myitsone having Chinese state enterprise as the biggest investor, in 2012, there was a cancellation in construction of coal-fired power plant in Dawei Project, in that time, developmental corporation of Thailand and Thai government was really interested in such project, in 2013, there was a suspension of Letpadaung Copper Mine Project having Chinese state enterprise as the investor as well; this copper mine project considered as the production source of copper to be provided for Chinese industry, especially weaponry manufacturing industry [27].

The foreign policy of Lao, in 2001, Thai and Lao government had a discussion which Thai government emphasized on the standing point not to support activities of anti Lao group. The closest relation with Lao is Vietnam as Vietnam supports an economic recovery in Lao, including reduction of custom duty for Lao goods as well.

Lao tried to search itself to improve strategy among the capitalism and globalization current by changing from socialism to open widely to capitalism through the new thinking policy since 1986. However, Lao economics in the present time still depends on international natural resource investment which, although, receives some criticism regarding following environment problems, Lao gains benefits from such investment. Lao changed investment regulations to be compliant with the regulations of WTF after gaining membership in 2011. Importantly, World Bank declared that the Lao People's Democratic Republic are proceeding in the way that will develop Lao to overcome the least developed country in 2020. At the present time, Lao utilizes 7th economic-development plan of 2011-2015 emphasizing on human resource development, improvement of good governance, providing facilitation for allowing economics sector, official sector and private sector having participation in economic development, including stipulating sustainable expansion in economics [28].

The foreign policy of Cambodia is more opened, having relation with China, Russia and USA. All 3 states went into Cambodia for trading, especially USA's company. As for the relation with Thailand, both parties promised to solve important problem in borderland issue. The main issue between Cambodia, Lao and Vietnam is that these 3 states have a negotiation in economic cooperation between each other which is a small alliance in large group of ASEAN in the future. The Prime Minister, Hun Sen and CCP political party would win in general election by 68 to 55 seats in the House of Representatives; however, there are 3 international relation issues which the opposition requests for adjustment and review policies and adjustment stance that has not to remain the same as these would cause shame and disadvantage in overall benefits of Cambodian, namely the relations with China, Vietnam and Thailand [29], [30].

VII. DISCUSSION

From the study results, it is found that all 10 ASEAN member states have the focus on different development according to environment, policy and readiness in several aspects of the states, which is in conformity with an adaptation

concept of ASEAN and sub-regional concept that the globalization economics emphasizing on movement that investor requires, that is to say, consistence of security in internal and external situations and fast connectivity with regions and sectors. The dispute between China and ASEAN member states will not expand to sanction level or termination of relations as the economic relation is still the significant factor regarding benefits which each parties can not terminate the relations. As for the relation between ASEAN and Superpowers outside of the region, although there are some conflicts, the relevant context between states has several aspects. An integration of small states group could help building a balance in negotiation with Superpowers. For other respect, the problem case affects other states in the region, ASEAN could not resolve by bilateral negotiation. For the foreign policy procedure, the basic of Game Theory, Decision Making Theory, and Systems Approach are environmental factors which are the determinant of framework in option in foreign policy; however, such option might change in the time according to environmental change and leader's idea.

Notices: Regarding the ASEAN context, could an application model in rule of law in Singapore inspire for other ASEAN member states to uphold the rule of law for developing the states and ASEAN region to be successful in economics and society or not? In order to find the answers, the consideration of ASEAN Way which is a foundation in performance of ASEAN and ASEAN Charter which escalates ASEAN level to be the international organization standing for rule-based principle must be applied but stipulated the decision making process of ASEAN based on consultant and consensus.

VIII. SUGGESTION

1. ASEAN must create consciousness of identity of the group that the member states are in the same group having shared group identity. If ASEAN can be like this, the cooperation will be created rapidly.
2. The sub-regional group should develop its group in trading and investment as it would be an advantage in history, culture and popularity of nearby states.
3. The leader of sub-regional group must jointly negotiate under ASEAN, which would strengthen ASEAN and develop technology and telecommunication between (ICT) under the group in order to cooperate more rapidly.

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